

Possible Speculation about Weird Isospin

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Abstract

Physics of strongly interacting particles are well known in terms of simplified mathematical models. This note seeks to propose some unusual ideas or simply new particles. The certainty of this paper must be an experimental approach in high energy accelerators or beyond.

Keywords: Isospin, Flavors, Baryon Number.

The supremacy of mathematical models describing particularly the strongly interacting particles is precise. The eightfold way [1] classification was proposed in 1961, which describes the patterns, mathematically established to classify the particles discovered in cosmic ray analysis. In 1968 the discovery of quarks gave the experimental vindication to firmly establish the existence of quarks. The work of Gell-Mann [2] predicted the possible existence of quarks of three flavors up, down and strange. However experiments showed that six flavors of quarks exist which bears an electric charge of $+2e/3$ and $-e/3$ with spin $\frac{1}{2}$ all clearly a fermions. The charge formula [3] derived by Gell-Mann and K.Nishijima is to calculate the charge of quarks of three flavors according to Gell-Mann's theory. The Gell-Mann-Nishijima formula relates the baryon number B , the strangeness S , the isospin I_3 of quarks to the electric charge Q

$$Q = I_3 + \frac{1}{2}(B + S)$$

But this formula holds good till standard model but in this paper it is our extreme probability speculation of something new type of particle whose properties can only be understood if they exist in nature (means when we observe it). The speculative calculation beyond any calculations performed in standard model suggest that a new range of particle or particles may exist which isospin quantum number or weak

isospin quantum number must be of $\frac{1}{4}$, means thoroughly different from something we have experienced in modern physics. Quarks possess an isospin of $+1/2$, $-1/2$ and 0 whereas weak isospin of left fermions makes $+1/2$ or $-1/2$ but however if this predicted isospin really exist then it will be the another goal for particle theorists and off course experimentalist in near future.

The author would like to thank Professor Amitava Raychaudhuri for his kind and useful criticism.

References

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